

Sentiment Analysis Of Student Feedback Using Natural Language Processing

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Abstract—This paper was created aspiring to use Natural language processing to be able to the Sentiment analysis in real time with high accuracy. Sentiment analysis is a technique for identifying the positivity, negativity, or neutrality of text data. In sentiment analysis, also referred to as opinion mining, affective states and subjective data are systematically identified, extracted, quantified, and analysed using text analysis and natural language processing. Sentiment analysis is frequently employed in marketing, customer service, clinical medicine, and other fields to examine comments and survey results, online and social media content, and healthcare materials. Sentiment analysis of service-based feedback is the goal of this paper. When you read student feedback you can immediately pick up on whether that student is happy, unhappy, neutral. You'll likely also be able to understand why they're feeling the way they are.

The process of fixing misspelt words in a text entails locating them and, occasionally, making suggestions. Words that might not be spelled correctly in a document will be highlighted by a programme called Spell Checker. When a piece of text is entered into a spell checker, it identifies the incorrect words by checking the dictionary to see if they are present. Last but not least, it provides dictionary suggestions for the incorrect words.

Keywords:Sentiment Analysis, Spelling Corrections, TextBlob, Flask, Support Vector Machine.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education professionals can use student feedback as a valuable resource for information to improve training activities and learning processes. It is a difficult task to deal with and process the opinions of the students. Using sentiment analysis and opinion mining techniques to their full potential is one way to overcome these difficulties. Finding words and phrases that express emotion through sentiment analysis is the process. The analysis of a student's behaviors toward a course topic, as well as the improvement of policies and higher education institutions, can both benefit from the use of sentiments as a source of information.

Spelling correction involves finding misspelt words in a text and, in some cases, making suggestions. It is a technique for identifying misspelt words in a text and sporadically making suggestions. Spell Checker is a computer programme that highlights words in a document that may not be spelled correctly. Text blocks produced by word processors and electronic dictionaries may be compatible with a standalone spell checker. Real-word errors and non-word errors are two different types of spelling errors.

Real-word mistakes are mistakes that are accepted dictionary words. Non-word errors are typos that use words that are not recognized by dictionaries.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The Support Vector Machines (SVM) algorithm is used for the sentiment analysis in the paper [1], and it produces highly accurate results. It has been demonstrated that this feedback gives teachers not only insightful information about how students learn but also a great chance to consider their own teaching methods and instructional materials.

According to the paper [2], one of the biggest problems with natural language processing is the use of non-English languages for sentiment analysis. In this work, we present a straightforward yet effective model that provides accurate results when quickly analyzing the feedback's sentiment in non-English languages.

Many unstructured data points are produced through comments and reviews in the paper [3]. Unstructured data analytics are unfortunately more difficult. storing these opinions in a structured database and using that to study how people respond. The goal of sentiment analysis is to examine and identify the feelings that underlie different people's opinions on various topics.

In paper [4], aim to tackle the problem of sentiment polarity categorization. Sentiment analysis or opinion mining is one of the major tasks of NLP (Natural Language Processing).

paper [5] focuses on previous work done by many authors in the same field.Using questionnaires that can provide more accurate and fast results.

III. METHODS AND MATERIALS

Other approaches to detect student feedback emotions, The majority of models face accuracy issues due to spelling mistakes and other issues .This paper develops a more user-friendly implementation and this approach may be used as a web application form and spelling mistakes can easily detect and solve it.

o Preprocessing Methods

The text documents in the datasets will be pre-processed, which includes stemming, lower case conversion, stop word

removal, tokenization, and stop word removal. The process of tokenizing involves separating a text into words, phrases, or other meaningful components, or tokens. Conjunctions, prepositions, and other words that are frequently used in texts but are unrelated to a particular subject are examples of stop words. Another pre-processing step is to convert all capital letters to lowercase. Before the classification stages, all uppercase characters are typically changed to their lowercase equivalents. The final step in the stemming procedure is to identify the root and stem of derived words.

○ Feature extraction

Feature extraction is the process of transforming input data into a collection of features. It is crucial to choose the extract features because the features of the machine learning process heavily influence its performance. The goal is to condense and transform the input data into a collection of representational features (features vectors) that are useful to the classifier.

○ Text Classification

Support Vector Machine (SVM) has been selected for the experiments' classification method. It is applied to categorise texts as either positive or negative. SVM's benefits, such as its capacity to handle large features, make it an effective tool for text classification.

A. Overall Design

In this paper, we create a sentiment analysis that accurately identifies student emotions. It has the ability to analyse a lot of feedback data. The Python modules TextBlob and Flask were used to build this system. The TextBlob can carry out operations based on natural language, like sentiment analysis and spelling checks. Positive, negative, and neutral sentiment are classified using the Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm.

The prerequisites software & libraries for the Sentiment analysis system are:

- Python (3.10.4)
- Flask (1.0.2)
- TextBlob
- NLTK

B. Techniques Used

(i) Support vector machine

Similar to how the Naive Bayes algorithm can be used for classification, the Support Vector Machines algorithm (SVM) can. Therefore, although it can also be used for regression, SVM is primarily used to classify data. It is a reliable algorithm that operates quickly even with little data.

fig 1: Support Vector Machine .

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to use natural language processing to predict emotions from text data. In natural language processing, the term "spelling correction" refers to the process of identifying and then correcting misspelt words. This system will be able to recognize misspelt words and comprehend sentiment.

The examples that follow serve as an explanation of how to determine the sentiment score of textual feedback.

- 1) Example Feedback1: Tough course, but he made sure we understood the material.
pre-processing: Tough course, made understood the material.
Negative : Tough
Positive : understood.
Score: 1-1 = 0 (Neutral)
- 2) Example Feedback2: No complaints at all, nice teacher.
pre-processing: no complaints nice teacher
Negative words: complaints
Positive words:
Score: 1-0 = 1 (Positive)
- 3) Example Feedback3 : This course's timings are not good.
pre-processing: course's timings not good.
Negative words:
Positive words: good
Score: 0-1 = -1 (Negative).

fig 2: Workflow of the system

fig 3.1.1 Postive Feedback

fig 3.1.2 Negative Feedback

fig 3.1.3 Neutral Feedback

fig 3.2 Spelling Correction

fig 4 Spelling Correction working diagram

fig 5 Error Correction

V. CONCLUSION

The goal of this study was to improve upon the initial team's design and can perform live Sentiment Analysis and Spelling correction of feedback using the SVM algorithm with high accuracy.

A future study will hopefully take it one step further and create a mobile application made available for download on Android and Apple platforms can Analysis text data in any language fast and efficiently.

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